

D6.1

COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION & EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

V0.3

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ABBREVIATIONS

C, D & E: Communication, dissemination and exploitation

HEU: Horizon Europe

KER: Key Exploitable Result

MCO: EHPA Manufacturers Committee

PUSH2HEAT: Pushing forward the market potential and business models of waste heat valorisation by full-scale demonstration of next-gen heat upgrade technologies in various industrial contexts.
R&I Committee: EHPA Research and Innovation Committee

WPs: Work Package (s)

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PARTNERS

TEC: Fundacion Tecnalia Research & Innovation

TECV: Tecnalia Ventures (Affiliated of TEC)

UPV: Universitat Politècnica de València

BSNOVA: BS Nova Apparatebau GmbH

SPH: SPH Sustainable Process Heat GmbH

VITO: Flemish Institute for Technological Research

FH: Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Foederung der Angewandten Forschung E.V

POLIMI: Politecnico di Milano

QPINCH: Qpinch NV

ENER: Enertime SA

ENCI: Enegy Circulaire (Affiliated of ENER)

TUB: Technische Universität Berlin

STC: Schoeller Technocell GmbH & Co KG

CARTIF: Fundación Cartif

OST: Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences (Associated Partner)

BONO: Bono Energia S.P.A

CDG: Cartiere di Guarcino S.P.A

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Stakeholders contact list template for consortium contacts collection	16
Figure 2: Official PUSH2HEAT logo.....	17
Figure 3: PUSH2HEAT disclaimer – non-editable version.....	18
Figure 4: PUSH2HEAT disclaimer – editable version.....	18
Figure 5: Push2Heat roadmap for KER development	30

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Preliminary stakeholder analysis	12
Table 2: Preliminary list of other like-minded projects to target.....	24
Table 3: Communication and dissemination KPI's.....	27
Table 4: Initial Key Exploitable Results.....	31

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABBREVIATIONS	4
PARTNERS.....	5
1. INTRODUCTION	9
2. OBJECTIVES.....	9
3. LANGUAGE.....	11
4. STAKEHOLDER GROUPS.....	11
4.1 Stakeholder analysis.....	12
4.2 Stakeholder Mapping.....	15
4.3 Stakeholder Network	15
4.4 External Advisory Board.....	16
5. COMMUNICATION CHANNELS.....	17
5.1 Visual identity	17
5.1.1 Dissemination templates.....	17
5.1.2 Disclaimer.....	18
5.2 Website.....	18
5.3 Project promotional materials & communication toolkit.....	19
5.4 Promotional videos.....	19
5.5 E-Newsletter.....	19
5.6 Social Media Channels.....	20
5.7 Project Media & Press Releases.....	21
6. DISSEMINATION CHANNELS	22
6.1 Scientific Publications.....	22
6.2 Participation in conferences & events.....	22
6.3 Networking activities	23
6.4 Collaboration with EU Projects	23
6.5 Policy Briefs.....	26
6.6 Demonstration cases & tools promotion.....	26
6.7 Dissemination multipliers	26
6.8 Final Conference	27
7. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION MONITORING.....	27

8. INTERNAL COMMUNICATION.....	28
9. EXPLOITATION STRATEGY.....	29
9.1 Initial Key Exploitable Results.....	31
9.2 Partner's strategy for exploitation.....	32
9.3 Activities & Roles.....	34
9.3.1 Roles.....	34
9.3.2 Workshops:.....	34
9.3.3 Monitoring and reporting:.....	34
ANNEXES.....	35
Annex 1: Dissemination activities repository.....	36
Annex 2: Agenda and minute taking template.....	37

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the European Commission's four main priorities as part of the new strategic agenda for the EU 2019-2024 is building a climate-neutral, green, fair, and social Europe, identifying "accelerating the transition to renewables and increasing energy efficiency" among the priority actions. Along the same line, the European Green Deal aims to build a carbon-neutral Europe by 2050.

Considering the weight that industrial process heat has in the total energy demand of the European industry, the first step towards decarbonization in the industrial sector is increasing energy efficiency through the recovery and upgrade of waste heat.

Despite the existence of heat pump technologies for heat upgrading, their wide deployment is not taking place due to various technical and non-technical barriers hindering the uptake. In this context, PUSH2HEAT will work towards overcoming these implementation barriers and push forward the market potential and business models of heat upgrade technologies by the full-scale demonstration of diverse heat upgrading heat pumps in relevant industrial sectors with high waste heat recovery and upgrading potential, as well as with a supply temperature range of 90-160°C.

This deliverable (D6.1) intends to present an overall impact-driven Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (C&D&E) strategy dedicated to raising awareness, promoting the PUSH2HEAT project and its related results, achievements, and knowledge generated within and beyond the course of the project.

It is prepared at an early stage of the project (M4) and will be updated to align with the project's progress (M16, M28, and M40). The strategy will be available to all project partners for reference and guidance. It has been developed with reference to the project proposal, the project Grant Agreement, EHPA's previous experience in communication and dissemination of EU project results, and the general guidelines contained in the documents below:

- "Communicating research for evidence-based policy-making – A practical guide for researchers in socio-economic sciences and humanities" (European Commission, 2011)
- "Communicating EU Research & Innovation: A guide for project participants" (European Commission, 2012).

2. OBJECTIVES

The communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy and plan aim to provide a clear overview of how all the communication channels and activities can work together to address the identified stakeholder groups.

The plan explains how and when the consortium will ensure the visibility of PUSH2HEAT as a project and maximize its impacts in terms of practical relevance, policy, market uptake, and research. Its activities will be discussed with the project partners on a regular basis to provide up-

to-date information and guarantee that the project materials are accessible to all, as well as that the messages communicated and disseminated are consistent.

EHPA as the Work Package leader of PUSH2HEAT's WP6 (Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation of project results), will coordinate the implementation of the activities described in this strategic document. However, it is vital to highlight that the strategy developed will not succeed without the full cooperation, direct involvement, and support of the other Work Package leaders and all the project partners.

WP6 will contribute to ensuring the transferability and sustainability of PUSH2HEAT's results. This will include: contributing to the transfer of knowledge, raising awareness, and supporting partners in processes necessary for future take-up, scale-up, and follow-up.

WP6 will also take the lead in adapting the technical and academic findings into more accessible content. Such (re)framing will be carried out in close collaboration with project partners to ensure the project's communication and dissemination resonates with different audiences.

The work of this plan will be divided into three areas:

- **Communication activities:** the focus will be on promoting the project's activities and raising awareness of the benefits of heat upgrading technologies to a general audience, including decision-makers.
- **Dissemination activities:** the focus will be spreading the technical results of PUSH2HEAT to identified target groups and fostering collaborations with other related projects.
- **Exploitation activities:** the focus will be on ensuring the life-beyond-the-project of PUSH2HEAT's generated results.

The overall goals of the strategy are:

- To disseminate PUSH2HEAT's results through various channels and to adapt technical language and research findings into appropriate messages for different audiences.
- To raise awareness of the industry's challenges and benefits of waste heat recovery and heat upgrading technologies.
- To facilitate regular flows of information within the consortium while supporting partners in effectively communicating and disseminating their work.
- To contribute to exchanges of information and experiences between organizations and to enable partners to receive regular updates from the demo sites.
- To inform and raise awareness about PUSH2HEAT's progress so that the heat upgrading technologies installed in the demo sites of the project become examples for others to follow by disseminating the project's generated knowledge among relevant stakeholders at EU, national and local levels.
- To educate and influence relevant stakeholders with the goal of having an impact on technology uptake, research, and legislative framework development.
- To lay the foundations for the wide-scale roll-out of Key Exploitable Results (KER)

As the project has different development phases, the approach to communication and dissemination will be different across each of them:

- **Phase I: Raise interest among key stakeholders:** establish a common project identity and raise awareness and interest regarding the project's expected results and impacts. The creation of a PUSH2HEAT stakeholder group will be fostered since the early stages of the project, as well as the creation of an External Advisory Group (EAG) described in T6.4.
- **Phase II: Enhance acceptance of Results:** Focus on disseminating KERs and engaging with key target audiences to raise awareness of the challenges and clearly demonstrate the benefits of implementing the new heat upgrade solutions.
- **Phase III: Foster uptake and replication of results:** facilitate the market uptake of the KERs and ensure continuous dissemination beyond the project timeframe. D&E&C activities will be organized around specific **working groups (WGs)** representing the identified target sectors. Under the coordination of **EHPA** (WP6 leader) the WGs will support the development of dedicated content, key messages, multiplication opportunities, and outward platforms to reach the relevant stakeholders, early adopters, and enablers and make them aware of the potential of heat upgrade technologies, the scope and capacity for their improvement and the steps needed towards mass deployment

3. LANGUAGE

The language of this project is English. For consistency, we recommend the use of British English spelling conventions where possible. Other languages are spoken in the consortium (Spanish, German, French, Italian) will be considered for the elaboration of communication materials.

We recommend partners read the [EC DG Translation English Language Style Guide](#).

4. STAKEHOLDER GROUPS

The communication and dissemination strategy cannot be separated from a thorough stakeholder analysis and mapping. The analysis and mapping process, whose rules, methods, and initial results are explored in this section, will pave the way to craft and use effective messages to reach the relevant target groups successfully. Furthermore, it will facilitate the communication and dissemination process and provide insight into the needs to engage with the different stakeholders by using adequate and integrated tools to ensure PUSH2HEAT's success.

The analysis and mapping need to be conducted with the Consortium partners and will be updated at several stages of the project (M16, M28, and M40) with potential new insights about the audiences.

4.1 Stakeholder analysis

The PUSH2HEAT Communication and Dissemination Strategy will be specifically aimed at reaching the target groups below. Key messages to communicate and value to be considered as key stakeholders has also been identified:

Table 1: Preliminary stakeholder analysis

Category	Stakeholders	Key messages and value
Industrial plant owners and new investors	Owners and operators of relevant industrial plants (food and beverage, paper, and chemical/pharmaceutical)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide comprehensive evidence on the advantages and impacts of the developed heat upgrade solutions - Main interested parties in fostering the uptake of heat upgrade solutions for more efficient, cleaner and cheaper operation of their plants.
	Potential new market entrants (investors): local businesses, SMEs, profit sector and finance, energy retailers and ESCOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential investors willing to enter/extend their presence into the industrial sustainability field.
Technology manufacturers platforms	National associations, clusters, and platforms of technology manufacturers (HP manufacturers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technology developers will foster collaboration and integrate competences and expertise on breakthroughs contributing to promoting and extending the impact of industrial heat upgrade projects. - National associations are key multipliers for technology development and project progress.

<p>Academia and research</p>	<p>Academia, RTOs, researchers, scientific community, and technical experts</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enable advancement in knowledge and further exploitation of project scientific results in future R&I initiatives, design of new specific R&D lines
<p>International sectoral platforms and initiatives</p>	<p>Platforms from relevant industrial sectors (e.g paper, food, chemical) and other Key players from related H2020 and HEU projects</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote knowledge sharing, engagement, new partnerships and complementarity with PUSH2HEAT - Boost outreach of a focused audience tackling similar challenges. - Enable the definition of a joint portfolio dissemination strategies - Enable the access to information and contribution to the EU and worldwide strategic agenda on industrial waste heat recovery and upgrade.
<p>Policy makers and public bodies/agencies</p>	<p>Local, regional and EU authorities and other policymakers; policy advisors (e.g. institutes and public agencies)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Key decision makers that will design the new policies and regulatory framework affecting the market roll-out of heat upgrade projects and technologies. - They need to be engaged and informed on the latest project developments (especially regarding T5.2, which deals with regulatory barriers in EU Member States and Associated Countries). - All consortium partners will engage with their local, National (priority being given to partners in demo site locations), and EU-level

		<p>policy-makers (priority being given to EHPA).</p>
<p>Financing entities</p>	<p>Public and private financing bodies (banks, regional governments, etc.) and EU initiatives coordinating investments in clean energy (SMARTSPEND, Ideas from Europe)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They play a major role in the replication and adoption of the heat upgrade technologies developed. - Focus on valuable data and results from demonstration projects, on the optimal blended financing approach and co-investment models to de-risk and trigger appropriate private investments.
<p>Civil society and media</p>	<p>Civil society organizations (CSOs), cooperatives, NGOs, consultancies, citizens, and media</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enable increasing awareness, acceptance and engagement on the economic, environmental, and social impacts fostered by PUSH2HEAT. - Facilitate new investment decisions to promote its market entrance. - Focus on engagement with NGOs (active in supporting climate neutrality challenges and a shift towards industrial sustainability) and media outreach as a major gateway to the general public.

The categories of stakeholders to reach are significantly represented by the consortium itself, which is composed of heat upgrading technology manufacturers, industrial end-users, business-oriented companies, research companies, universities, and representatives of the heat pump industry. This factor will guarantee a more thorough identification of the key messages to be communicated carried out by partners themselves and access to a complete contact network to be used in communication and dissemination activities.

4.2 Stakeholder Mapping

A stakeholder mapping will be carried out, monitored, and updated throughout the course of the project to identify the most relevant players in the target groups defined above. An initial list will be created starting from contacts from Project Consortium partners' networks belonging to identified stakeholder groups.

As WP6 leader, EHPA will actively disseminate the project objectives, activities, and results within EHPA Research and Innovation Committee. The R&I Committee has more than 110 and provides an opportunity to share information on HP Research and Innovation. The initiative's goal is to establish a group and promote synergies between group members. PUSH2HEAT will be disseminated during the periodic meetings of the committee to grow its outreach.

In addition, EHPA will introduce PUSH2HEAT in the EHPA Manufacturers Committee (MCO). This committee has more than 100 members and aims to provide a platform for manufacturers in the association to discuss topics relevant to manufacturers. It defines and suggests areas of strategic interest to the manufacturers. Presenting the project during one of the MCO periodic meetings could add value to the project and the MCO members. It would contribute to expanding the stakeholder network of the project and therefore, increase the transferability of the outcomes.

4.3 Stakeholder Network

The stakeholder mapping will be the base to develop a stakeholder network that will maximize the project's dissemination and communication. The stakeholder network will be built progressively during the project's lifecycle, and it will gather stakeholders interested in PUSH2HEAT's activities.

An initial list will be created starting from contacts from Project Consortium partners' network. Each partner is committed to promoting the project through their own website, newsletters, social media pages, and any other communication they might use with the final goal of involving interested actors in the project in their network. A form will be included on the PUSH2HEAT website for stakeholders to register to the network. Those who registered will have access to the project newsletter and will periodically receive information on the PUSH2HEAT's activities (e.g., webinar, publications, news).

Contacts will be mobilized by the direct owner of the emails/contacts (starting from an already established collaboration) to avoid conflicts with the GDPR. PUSH2HEAT Social media channels, Twitter and LinkedIn, will serve as a means to encourage the public to join the Stakeholder network. In addition, participants in PUSH2HEAT events that show interest in participating further in the project at the registration stage will be added to the Stakeholder network.

5. COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

The PUSH2HEAT communication strategy will spread the project's vision towards a broader community of stakeholders that can benefit from integrating industrial heat upgrading technologies beyond those addressed and into transversal sectors such as building heating. The focus of all communication activities within the PUSH2HEAT project is, therefore, increasing the economic impact of those innovations carried out within the project by promoting them and the project, using the resources, networks, and expertise of all consortium partners, to various audiences, including groups beyond the project's internal communities to wider quadruple helix audiences (public authorities, industry, academia, and citizens), as well as raising awareness of the challenges, technical and economic benefits of heat upgrading and the technologies associated with it.

The main communication channels that will be utilized during the project is presented below:

5.1 Visual identity

A common branding will be developed during the first months of the project (by M4) to ensure an immediate recognition of the project. The logo, as the visual messenger of the project, will be used by all templates, reports, and dissemination activities throughout the project. The official PUSH2HEAT logo (see Figure 1) was selected to represent the project via an online poll by the majority of the voting partners.

Figure 2: Official PUSH2HEAT logo

5.1.1 Dissemination templates

Based on the visual identity, to be approved by all the partners of the consortium, templates for Microsoft Word, Microsoft PowerPoint, and Microsoft Excel will be developed by EHPA. PUSH2HEAT partners will use these during the project for presentations, reporting, newsletters, etc. The templates will be developed following any applicable rules and regulations of the European Commission.

5.1.2 Disclaimer

As included in PUSH2HEAT's PUSH2HEAT's Grant Agreement, all the material used in the Communication and Dissemination of the project must contain the EU Disclaimer. All partners are invited to use the following disclaimer:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101069689 (PUSH2HEAT)

Figure 3: PUSH2HEAT disclaimer – non-editable version

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No.101069689

Figure 4: PUSH2HEAT disclaimer – editable version

5.2 Website

A website for PUSH2HEAT will be developed in the early stages of the project (M4). The website will be the main communication and dissemination platform, allowing stakeholders and others to access the project aims, development, and results. It will reflect the support of the EU Commission. All information will be secure and follow GDPR requirements.

The website will be maintained by EHPA, the partner responsible for uploading the relevant content during the project Lifecycle and up to two years after its completion. However, all partners will be involved in developing content to provide visibility to the project and maximize its impact.

The website will give access to all public deliverables, the bi-annual newsletter and promote relevant content (news, videos, events...) for the key stakeholder groups. It will be regularly updated to include the significant flow of research and policy briefs and will also host the resources developed under the other WPs, for example: WP4 – Guidelines for heat upgrade technologies design and integration and the evaluation tool for go/no-go decision making.

The website will also be the host of a Training Campaign consisting of webinar recordings and virtual demo-sites visits. At least 8 trainings (4 webinars + 4 demo visits) will be provided by R&D partners in collaboration with demo-site leaders and technology providers.

To increase its outreach, it will be directly connected to the project's social media profiles (LinkedIn, Twitter) for a wider dissemination to technical and non-technical audience and linked to all consortium partners websites.

5.3 Project promotional materials & communication toolkit

The PUSH2HEAT brochure will be developed to raise awareness and provide visibility to the project among the large non-specialist community as well as the community of the relevant stakeholders. It will be distributed to partner's organizations (to be further distributed through their networks and channels) and on public events. Printouts will be kept to a minimum for environmental reasons, and those materials printed will include QR (Quick Response) codes that can be easily scanned via smartphone and provide access to materials and different virtual resources such as the website and the e-newsletter subscription.

Two versions of the communication toolkit will be elaborated:

- An initial version developed shortly after the beginning of the project focusing on raising awareness and provide visibility to the project (M4)
- A mid-term version oriented to disseminate initial project results. (M24)

All partners will need to provide inputs as the toolkit requires to synthesize the aims and ambitions of the project.

5.4 Promotional videos

Video content will be used as well to increase the visibility of the project. Two promotional videos will be prepared during the project: the first one will be produced by M8, and it will detail the project's work program; the second one, by M46, will focus on presenting the project's key outputs. These will be used on all the relevant communication channels to ensure the key stakeholders are exposed to their messages. Using content obtained from research tasks – and used for crafting the policy briefings – short 60-second videos that briefly answer a project-related question might be produced to be disseminated through social media channels and in short presentations.

5.5 E-Newsletter

A bi-annual newsletter will be created to provide updated information about the project to the relevant key stakeholders. The newsletter will be sent electronically and uploaded on the project website, and consortium partners will share it via their respective mailing lists/in their respective e-newsletters.

The objectives of the newsletters are:

- Informing stakeholders of the key findings of the project.
- Providing information related to relevant external events and publications.
- Disseminating key messages from the Work Package leaders.

The design of the newsletter will be in-line with the pre-defined visual identity.

A proposed structure for the newsletter could be the following:

- PUSH2HEAT update: provide a comprehensible update of where the project stands (e.g., milestones achieved, deliverables, outputs, events...)
- News & Events: short items about relevant events and developments on the project
- Reading recommendations: selected documents/research suggested by WP Leaders and all partners relevant to PUSH2HEAT's work. Include the title, author, link, and a short synopsis.

7 Newsletters are planned throughout the project. A suggested schedule to follow could be:

- April 2023
- October 2023
- April 2024
- October 2024
- April 2025
- October 2025
- April 2026

5.6 Social Media Channels

[Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#) will be the main social media channels to disseminate PUSH2HEAT's work because of the possibilities they offer to reach the stakeholder groups of interest. Core topics to be addressed in social media could be related to PUSH2HEAT's main areas: heat upgrade technologies, industrial heat pumps, renewable energy, energy efficiency. Other topics that could be addressed would be: PUSH2HEAT updates, PUSH2HEAT's results, relevant events/seminars, project related questions.

Initially the social media accounts will share posts related to where PUSH2HEAT will be presented as well as posts from other accounts, to build a community of interest and, consequently, creating an audience to share results to.

Original content will help to increment the reach and traffic of the used social media channels, and consequently, the website. Therefore, it is crucial for the Consortium partners to contribute to the content to be published for effective dissemination of PUSH2HEAT on social media.

Partners will be encouraged to use the hashtag #PUSH2HEAT as well as to tag the project in the related posts they make on their own accounts.

5.7 Project Media & Press Releases

Press releases will be written by the WP6 partners at crucial points in the project's developments and sent to relevant news outlets. They will be drafted and circulated among the relevant partners for review and comments.

At least 4 press releases are foreseen throughout the project. Each of them will aim at generating interest about the project's activities.

Each partner can issue its own press releases but needs to inform all partners, specially WP6 leader (EHPA) beforehand to ensure accuracy and consistency of the information. Information will be collected for reporting purposes as well as to make sure that the key stakeholder groups are effectively reached.

PUSH2HEAT will also seek to be presented on generalist/specialist media, such as local or national press, magazines, radio, podcasts or TV programmes. Specialist media will be used to reach specific stakeholder groups based on their potential role in the project's replication activities.

6. DISSEMINATION CHANNELS

6.1 Scientific Publications

PUSH2HEAT partners will publish the most relevant results in scientific literature, dedicated journals and magazines that will give EU and international project spread. The publications will follow the agreed IPR protection strategy. Journals from international reference scientific editorials and repositories (e.g ELSEVIER, ASME, IEEE, EPRI, MDPI) as well as relevant technical literature at the national level will be considered. At least 10 scientific publications will be elaborated.

6.2 Participation in conferences & events

PUSH2HEAT, and its results, will be presented in several EU and international forums and events related with the scope of the project in order to boost consortium and results visibility.

Events identified for the PUSH2HEAT project in an initial stage are as follows:

- European Heat Pump Summit
- EHPA Annual Heat Pump Forum (including the Heat Pump Award)
- IEA Heat Pump Conference
- WSED – World Sustainable Energy Days
- Sustainable Places
- EUSEW – EU Sustainable Energy Week
- ICAE – International Conference on Applied Energy
- Chillventa
- ISH Messe Frankfurt
- ICR - International Congress of Refrigeration

All partners are encouraged to present PUSH2HEAT at external events to increase the impact of the project. The coordinator must be always informed beforehand about the planned presentations and their content. When necessary, to ensure accuracy and consistency, the presentation content will be developed in cooperation with the coordinator.

Furthermore, 2 dedicated workshops, linked with EU and private annual events to increase their scope and reach the relevant audience, will be designed, and implemented for research stakeholders. In addition, WP6 leader, EHPA, will present PUSH2HEAT to its Heat Pump Manufacturers, Research and Innovation Committees and Industrial and Commercial Heat Pumps Working Groups.

A document to collect the dissemination activities of all the partners will be developed. The document should be filled up every month by all partners to gather all the dissemination activities that have taken place throughout the project:

- Posts done on the partners' social media accounts
- Post done on the partners websites
- Press releases
- Presentations in events
- Meetings with policy makers...

The information collected will be used for reporting purposes and to monitor that all target groups are reached.

6.3 Networking activities

Fostering networking will allow project partners to learn from each other, discuss common issues they might be experiencing and get feedback on their work. WP6 Leader EHPA will encourage partners to disseminate further the project through their own social and professional networks (Linkedin, Twitter, Youtube, Xing...) to create discussion, solve doubts and attract future investors. Other networking activities foreseen during the project is the organization of virtual matchmaking sessions and national roundtables in which stakeholders will benefit from the interaction with policy makers and funding agencies.

- 2 National Roundtables – planned in T5.5- gathering policy makers from local, National and EU levels to provide their inputs on regulatory barriers and recommendations for adaptation and improvement of legislation.
- 2 virtual matchmaking sessions in collaboration with funding agencies and initiatives such as Horizon2020 SMARTSPEND (coordinating investments in clean energy R&D), Ideas from Europe, the EU Commission and other funding bodies at the EU level...

Other effective means of disseminating information on the project advances and results at EU and national levels will be identified by all partners.

6.4 Collaboration with EU Projects

During the project, close links with other projects will be established.- EHPA will promote the joint participation with other like-minded projects (e.g. projects from HE clusters 4 and 5, the LIFE subprogramme on energy transition, other already running H2020 projects, etc.) and members of

Hubs4Circularity. Partners will be encouraged to contribute with their project suggestions, and EHPA will coordinate the data collection from partners.

The collaboration with other projects will be established by the coordinator and/or EHPA.

Workshops will be used as tools to foster collaboration among projects. They will be designed to reach an international audience; they will be livestreamed (via MS TEAMS) and recorded and made available for all participants and interested stakeholders.

Table 2: Preliminary list of other like-minded projects to target:

Project name	Topic	Start-end dates	CORDIS page
MODERATE- Marketable Open Data Solutions for Optimized Building-Related Energy Services	HORIZON-CL5- 2021-D4-01-03 - Advanced data-driven monitoring of building stock energy performance	1st June 2022 – 31st May 2026	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069834
CHRONICLE - Building Performance Digitalisation and Dynamic Logbooks for Future Value- Driven Services	HORIZON-CL5- 2021-D4-01-01 - Advanced energy performance assessment and certification	1st July 2022- 31st December 2025	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069722
INPERSO - INdustrialised and PErsonalised Renovation for Sustainable sOcieties	HORIZON-CL5- 2021-D4-01-02 - Industrialisation of deep renovation workflows for energy- efficient buildings	1st July 2022 – 30th June 2026	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069820

<p>InCUBE - An INCIUsive toolBox for accElerating and smartening deep renovation</p>	<p>HORIZON-CL5-2021-D4-01-02 - Industrialisation of deep renovation workflows for energy-efficient buildings</p>	<p>1st July 2022- 30th June 2026</p>	<p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069610</p>
<p>SmartLivingEPC- Advanced Energy Performance Assessment towards Smart Living in Building and District Level</p>	<p>HORIZON-CL5-2021-D4-01-01 - Advanced energy performance assessment and certification</p>	<p>1st July 2022- 30th June 2025</p>	<p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069639</p>
<p>High-Quality Data-Driven Services for a Digital Built Environment towards a Climate-Neutral Building Stock</p>	<p>HORIZON-CL5-2021-D4-01-03 - Advanced data-driven monitoring of building stock energy performance</p>	<p>1st June 2022 – 31st May 202</p>	<p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069658</p>
<p>SPIRIT- Implementation of sustainable heat upgrade technologies for industry</p>	<p>HORIZON-CL5-2021-D4-01 - Full-scale demonstration of heat upgrade technologies with supply temperature in the range 90 - 160°C</p>	<p>1st September 2022 – 28th February 2026</p>	<p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069672</p>
<p>DECAGONE - DEmonstrator of industrial CARbon-free power</p>	<p>HORIZON-CL5-2021-D4-01-05 - Industrial excess (waste) Heat-to-Power</p>	<p>1st June 2022 – 31st May 2026</p>	<p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069740</p>

Generation from Orc-based waste-heat-to-Energy systems	conversion based on organic Rankine cycles		
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6.5 Policy Briefs

These materials will reflect the key areas being addressed in PUSH2HEAT's work program. They will be elaborated at varying levels of detail depending on the target group addressed. Each research task will include the drafting of relevant briefs – from early phase of research and when results are available- and EHPA will oversee editing.

Special emphasis will be placed on data visualization (infographics) for facilitating the readability of the project's outputs.

6.6 Demonstration cases & tools promotion

The demonstration cases will be used for dissemination of the project's achievements and as base for the training campaign foreseen (to take place on the website) under the guidance of the respective demo lead partners.

There will be at least a workshop organized with all demo sites and 1 showcase program promoting demo sites as dissemination and training assets.

6.7 Dissemination multipliers

For further increasing the awareness and impacts of PUSH2HEAT, it is vital that partners exploit the platforms they are already members of as dissemination multipliers: EERA, A.SPIRE, Sustainable Places, ETIP-RHC, SET Plan, HE Partnerships such as Built4People, CETP and DUT (Partners to add more examples of platforms they are part of). Representatives of the selected platforms will be invited to participated in the project's events.

Moreover, to ensure the impact of the project, at least 3 other workshops will be organized jointly with W4RES (a network committed to gender equality in the European energy sector) and/or other initiatives bringing together local/regional policymakers such as CELSIUS and FEDARENE.

6.8 Final Conference

The final conference will be organized the last month of the project to bring together stakeholders from all relevant fields. It will be linked to the EHPA Heat Pump Forum, a flagship event that brings together experts from business communities, universities, research centres, EU policy and investment decision makers, media and relevant energy/renewable heating and cooling stakeholders, where PUSH2HEAT will have been presented each year since its start.

The content of the final conference will be discussed and determined in close collaboration with all the partners.

7. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION MONITORING

Table 3: Communication and dissemination KPI's

Channel	KPIs
Website	Visits: <5000= Poor; 5000-10000= good; >10000=Excellent Material downloads: <50 = Poor; 50-100=good; >100= excellent
Brochure/leaflet	Distribution: <500 e-copies = Poor; 500-1000 e-copies=good; >1000 e-copies = excellent
Social media	At least 200 followers attracted and engaged
Press Releases	At least 4 published
Conferences, fairs, events	At least 3 per year
Workshops	At least 3 workshops with communication multipliers

Networking activities	At least 2 National Round-Tables for policy makers At least 2 virtual matchmaking sessions with funding agencies
Newsletter	7 issues
Scientific publications	At least 10
Training Campaign	Attendees: <80 = Poor; 80-120 =good; >120= excellent 8 trainings (4 webinars + 4 demovisits) provided by R&D partners in collaboration with demo leaders and technology providers
Demonstration cases and tools (part of training campaign)	1 workshop with all demosites 1 showcase program promoting demos as dissemination and training assets

8. INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

Internal communication plays a vital role in ensuring an efficient execution of the project to maximize results. It is key to guarantee clear communication among partners and facilitate the exchange of ideas and interaction between work packages.

The main tools used by partners for periodic communication will be:

- SharePoint: managed by Tecnalia, it is the tool selected for internal exchange of documents, results and for facilitating collaborative work.
- Teams: to host video-calls among the different partners.
- Emails: a project mailing list has been created by Tecnalia that includes information on which contact person should receive emails for every work package.

The members of the consortium will have the chance to communicate through:

- Consortium meetings: held twice a year physically. All partners need to participate as they are an opportunity to update the whole consortium on the state of the project and discuss the upcoming steps.
- Project coordinator and WP leaders meetings: held every two months.
- Internal Work Package meetings: held depending on need, each WP decides whether to have meetings with the partners involved in their WP.

The involvement of all partners is key for a successful dissemination of the project, every partner will allocate time to dissemination and communication activities. Partners should support dissemination by:

- Making presentations referring to the project/about the project at conferences and other events and sharing them within the consortium partners
- Keeping records of all their dissemination activities (such as presentations in an event) as these will be needed for reporting purposes
- Using their company's communication tools to support the dissemination of PUSH2HEAT (website, newsletters, social media accounts...)
- Linking PUSH2HEAT's website to their own websites
- Inviting colleagues/interested parties to sign up for the PUSH2HEAT's newsletter and follow the project on our social media channels.
- Circulating PUSH2HEAT's materials (e.g. leaflets, policy briefs, reports) to colleagues/potential interested parties that are not yet on the project's mailing list.

9. EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

The exploitation strategy followed in PUSH2HEAT aims to ensure a life-beyond-the-project for all the generated results and is given by the following cornerstones:

Identification of Key Exploitable Results (KER):

A key exploitable result is that which has a commercial or social significance (i.e., provide knowledge or economic profit). In PUSH2HEAT, these are not limited to complete systems and prototypes, therefore, the consortium will also exploit sub-systems, components, procedures, models, and other assets developed in the project. For each of the key exploitable results, a lead partner is identified, who will be leading the updating of the identification and assessment with regards to that result. Obtain a clear idea of which partner will contribute to achieving each result. The initial list of KER is in section 9.1. New KER can be generated along the project life and for that different versions of the KER list can exist in PUSH2HEAT.

Roadmap towards characterization and exploitation of KER:

With the objective of expressing future intentions of partners regarding each KER, which will facilitate discussions on commercialization or intellectual property issues. For all the KERs, the following information will be collected from the relevant partners using a questionnaire: KER description, initial and expected TRL, type of outcome, Plan on exploiting the project results after the end of the project. Innovative results will be identified and KERs in which a high TRL is achieved a go to market strategy should be established at the end of the project by explicating the attractiveness to the potential markets/users, key benefits or problems solved by this new technology/product, risk analysis and expected time to market as an input for the business models and partners agreements developed in WP5.

Intellectual Property protection and rights:

Connected to the desired exploitation a protection strategy should be set accordingly with the following content:

- IPR'S ON BACKGROUND INFORMATION (B) Information, excluding foreground information, brought to the project from existing knowledge, owned or controlled by project partners in the same or related fields of the work carried out in the research project.
- IPR'S ON FOREGROUND INFORMATION (F) Information generated by the project partners or 3rd parties working for them in the implementation of the research project.
- Protection strategy (patent, secret, copyright etc.)
- Who has which rights to which exploitable results and under which Terms & Conditions contribution of each partner and distribution of ownership, exploitation plan.

Connection to EC Initiatives on high potential results:

PUSH2HEAT connects KER with EC Innovation Radar by identifying the innovative results of the project and with Horizon Results Platform by distinguishing the innovative results with high potential value to be exploited. (see KER roadmap in Figure 1).

Figure 5: Push2Heat roadmap for KER development

9.1 Initial Key Exploitable Results

A set of Key Exploitable Results with the highest potential for fast commercial roll-out was identified during the proposal writing stage and is given in Table 4.

Table 4: Initial Key Exploitable Results

	KER	Result	Partner(s)	Type*	Exploitations modes*	Time to market
1	Up-scaled HTHP with piston compressor	R1	SPH	T	IPD, DS	1 year
2	Large-scale HTHP with centrifugal compressors	R2	ENER	T	IPD, DS, P	+2 years
3	Up-scaled Absorption Heat Transform (HP Type II)	R3	BSNOVA, TEC, TUB	T	IPD, DS, Pub	2 years
4	Thermochemical Heat Transformer for heat upgrade until 160°C	R4	QPINCH, VITO	T	IPD, DS, Pub	2 years
5	Guidelines for integration and open access evaluation tool	R6	OST	IS, M, R	CS, K, L, Pub	1 year
6	Open access monitoring data	R9	FH, POL, TEC	D	K	0,5 years

* S – Software; IS – Integrated Software; M – Models; T – Technology

** P – Patent; CS – Consultancy services; DS – Direct Sale; L – License; K – Knowhow; IPD – Internal Product development; Pub - Publications

9.2 Partner's strategy for exploitation

The All PUSH2HEAT partners are fully committed to exploit their results after project's end. Depending on partners' activities focus will be different. A summary of individual partners' exploitation strategy is provided in Table 2.

Table 5: Partners' intentions for exploitation

Type of partner	Partners involved	Individual exploitation intentions
Technology providers	SPH, ENER, BSNOVA, QPINCH	<p>Commercialize their product developments to reach certain level of specific installations of the new heat upgrade systems</p> <p>1–2-year industrialization time to commercialize their technologies</p> <p>New products will enable commercial agreements with ESCOs to apply adapted business models tested within the project</p>
	TUB, TEC, VITO	<p>Reinforce the R&D collaboration with technology manufacturers exploring joint access to market and provision of consultancy services for industrial partners willing to integrate the technologies</p> <p>VITO will expect to exploit its software for heat exchanger design and optimisation to contract research and consultancy services to heat exchanger designers, manufacturers and other interested parties.</p> <p>TUB expect to exploit its control software algorithms to contract research and development agreements with other interested parties.</p>
Owners of industrial facilities	STC, CDG	Maintaining the heat upgrade implementations to obtain the highest economic benefit of their productive core business by reducing energy costs.

		Apply continuous control and optimization of related assets, extracting further knowledge and evaluating replication of the PUSH2HEAT solutions in same/similar plants
Engineering, consulting companies and clusters	ENCI	Increase energy and innovation management services by the application of PUSH2HEAT's knowledge Specific joint market approach with ENER, to new industrial customers
	BONO	Lessons learnt from design and commissioning phases of PUSH2HEAT technologies into CDG demo site as well as the contents of the integration guideline and open access evaluation tool is expected to help getting new engineering contracts for industrial heat upgrade projects.
	EHPA	EHPA will foster their dissemination and communication activities within the European Heat Pump sector and will use PUSH2HEAT experience to improve advisory/consultancy services to their associates.
Research and academia	TEC, FH, POLIMI	As responsible partners for the performance monitoring of the demo cases, they will use this valuable database to publish scientific papers (one of its core missions) and support new industrial partners to implement innovative solutions based on PUSH2HEAT results to support facing their decarbonization challenges. The techno-economic performance map and LCA results led by TEC will help pursue this exploitation goal.
	OST, UPV, CAR, TECV	The focus will be on the exploitation of WP5 results, including model-based replication case studies, impact assessments, and adapted business models and contracts that have been identified and tested. These will be published in open-access research journals and disseminated within local partner networks to promote new research initiatives and partnerships (e.g., the Swiss national project SWEET DeCarbCH). Business model descriptions and guidelines for integration will be used for consultancy of further companies in similar situations as the industrial project partners. In addition, TECV will act as a promoter of go-to-market strategies for the PUSH2HEAT results supporting industrial partners through innovation management services while aiming at establishing commercial partnerships.

9.3 Activities & Roles

To develop the presented exploitation strategy, roles defined and main activities that will be carried out along the project are described as follows:

9.3.1 Roles

The project coordinator (TEC), with the support of the exploitation manager (TECV) will guide the consortium to deal with the protection of IPR and the definition of business plans defined in WP5, which will lay the foundation for the consortium's exploitation strategy.

9.3.2 Workshops:

3 exploitation workshops will be organized at initial, mid-term and final project phases to address:

- A detailed definition of the exploitable results
- The development of the replication and exploitation strategy: defining what, who, how, barriers and ownership of every exploitable results
- The final definition of IPR and exploitable results

The goals of this workshops will be to:

- Discuss the most promising exploitable results and first hypothesis related to potential related business plans
- Obtain an agreement for the final exploitation actions

9.3.3 Monitoring and reporting:

KERs will be updated periodically and reported in the annual project reports.

Deliverable D6.3 "Exploitation report: Key results, project innovations and post project strategy" will contain the status of KER at the end of the project with the go to market strategy for the most developed ones (higher TRL and higher market potential).

ANNEXES

Annex 1: Dissemination activities repository

Partner	Event title	What is it? Workshop, meeting, conference, social media post...	Link	Date	Location	Name of the presenter	Methods used to present PUSH2HEAT (Flyers, roll up, ppt)	No. People reached	Target group	Status: Performed or Planned

Annex 2: Agenda and minute taking template

XXXX Meeting

WPX –

Details

Time: dd/mm/yyyy

Location: xxxx

Meeting link – if online

Participants

Meeting called by: XXX

Minutes taken by: XXX

Participants: XXX

Agenda

10:00	Lorem ipsum	Presenter
10:05	Lorem ipsum	Presenter
10:10	Lorem ipsum	Presenter
10:15	Lorem ipsum	Presenter

10:25	Lorem ipsum	Presenter
10:30	Lorem ipsum	Presenter
10:50	Lorem ipsum	Presenter
11:30	Lorem ipsum	Presenter
11:45	Lorem ipsum	Presenter
11:55	Lorem ipsum	Presenter
12:00	Lorem ipsum	Presenter
